

Strategic Triangles: Why Europe faces a Choice Dilemma under the Post-cold war US-China competition in Africa?

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Abstract

The Post-Cold War International system has gone from unipolar to quasi bipolar world order and slowly gravitating towards multipolarity. While Europe is often presented as a great power, US-China worldwide dynamics dominate headlines despite Covid-19 pandemic and Climate change emergencies. This paper explains why Europe faces a choice dilemma regarding its interest and actions in Africa under US-China competition for World Primacy. Early findings suggest that China's presence in Africa serves European core interests. The ongoing US-China competition negatively affects the China-Africa Angle of cooperation. Europe faces a serious choice dilemma to pursue and achieve its immediate and long-term interests. It is divided into what is worth name European Western-Eastern choice dilemma.

Keywords: US-China competition for World Primacy, Europe in Africa, Choice Dilemma.

While American liberal world order believers, with fanfare, assumed to end history (Fukuyama 1989) by promoting combined western values in the entire world, it was at the dawn of the 21st century, without fanfare, that China's return shook the unipolar moment and inaugurated the continuation of power politics. It is worth recalling that if the American Gulf war launched the "*Unipolar moment* (Charles 1990) (John 1990)", *the Trade War* inaugurates today's "*quasi-bipolarity moment*" international system. China's political leadership and continuous economic growth (fueled by its entry into WTO) contributing to mitigate adverse effects of 2008's global financial crises and the 2014 IMF World economic outlook projections of China's economic might in terms of purchasing power parity terms constitutes a key event of structural transformation in the post-cold war international system. More importantly, China's striving for achievement policy (Yan 2014) is equally a decisive factor in inaugurating China's new behaviour and making the US-China competition for World primacy very complex and uncertain.

The US-China competition for world primacy is driven by two thousand years of realpolitik; that is: an emerging power (China) threatens the existing superpower's (the U.S) status quo. Hence, status quo power is usually paranoid of the emerging power and power transition (Olemanu 2021). The Harvard distinguished Professor Graham Alison illustrated 16 case studies of power conflict in the book *Destined for war: can America and China escape Thucydides's trap?* (Graham 2017). From his illustration, it is evident why US-China are now engaged in a worldwide competition. Secondly, the competition is lead by the Yellow peril dictates. It looks at the way humans make decisions. Yellow peril is concerned about things driven by emotions, conscious or unconscious. The Singaporean distinguished Professor Kishore Mahbubani has brilliantly pointed out that: "emotions play as important a role as a reason in international relations" (Kishore 2020). This has implications on the already US-China strategic competition. For five centuries, western powers, today lead by the U.S., have designed the world on their self-image. Will they easily adjust and adapt to the world new realities? For instance, China (a non-western power) has become a significant player and increasingly leads the rest's rise (Kishore,

2005). Will the U.S. accommodate China peacefully? That is what drives the US-China competition for world primacy more dangerous and unpredictable.

Recent scholarly literature presents Europe, among others, as a great power (Report 2015) with particularly ground in Africa (Acharya 2014). History suggests that Europe has played a mitigating role in Africa from the 15th century to nowadays. European Africa's interactions have been at the centre of world affairs (Ndayweill 2009). While Asia-Pacific is seen as the primary area of US-China competition for world primacy, Africa is perceived as a continent dependent on European peace in the new century. Recent research has shown how much Africa can destabilize Europe more than any other continent in the world. For instance, the adverse effects of Climate change, poverty, terrorism and lousy governance constitute a considerable asset for young African immigration to Europe. Although China's strategic move in Africa, since 1990, has promoted and driven a relative amelioration of social conditions. Today's worldwide US-China competition negatively affects China's evolving economic and infrastructure cooperation in Africa (Olemanu 2021).

Drawing from this observation, the paper briefly presents China's return and the Rising Africa story, the European interests in Africa to capture and elucidate why Europe faces a choice dilemma under US-China competition for world primacy.

The Return of China and the Rising Africa Story

China's return in global affairs recalls that from year 1 up to 1820, China and India were the world's largest economies. To put it clear, before the dawn of colonialism in China and India, China and India accounted for nearly 60 percent of the world economy for the first 1,500 years A.D. (Kishore, 2018) and are projected to account for about 40 percent of the world output in 2050 (Acharya 2014). Current geopolitical realities suggest that the centre of the world economy

moves from Europe and America to China and India. So, today's China's overall prowess: 15 per cent of global GDP, the second largest economy, gravitational centre for the developing world, initiated vast and ambitious projects, contributes to more than 30 percent to world economic growth, the world's largest and industrial country, military strength, social confidence and social-cultural influence should be understood (like in China) as a determinant signal of a China's return in world affairs. Whatever be the political discourse, China's post-cold war strategic move has brought something tangible in Africa through numerous investments, loans, and businesses of all kinds (Olemanu 2021).

Although it is challenging to evaluate the positive impact of China's engagement in Africa, it is worth noting that China has contributed visibly towards Africa's rise. Through infrastructure investments, state-building, promotion of economic development, supporting harmonization of social conditions, is enabling sustained economic growth, managing the continental debt, and abundant human resource (Deborah 2010).

The African Rise is more than a story and a tangible discourse drawn from observation. Post-colonialism and neo-colonization, plenty of sufferings were driven by wars, military coups, pandemics, economic recession, dictatorship, and external interferences on internal affairs. The dawn of the 21 first century coinciding with China's strategic involvement in Africa (Olemanu 2021) is perceived by many Africans as a moment for overall transformation to change the infernal cycle they were bound to. Of course, evaluation differs from country to country. Some countries took advantage, while others were handicapped by bad governance. Since 2008, almost all African nations have been impacted by U.S. interference and the US-China rivalry in the region. For instance, the mitigated result in the Democratic Republic of Congo, where the U.S. opposed the Sicomines agreement labeled *Contrat Chinois* from its inception (Olemanu 2021).

European Immediate and Long-term Interests in Africa

Geopolitically speaking, Europe is a fragmented continent where interests are diverse and, to some extent, differently. However, the European Union and certain countries, namely France and Germany, promote European interests for continental survival. Therefore, strengthening these interests is the first goal of E.U.'s delegation worldwide, especially in Africa.

The post-independence European-African interaction was dominated by a paternalistic approach fueled by the chronic instability of several African countries (Kabemba 2016). After independence, most African leaders found themselves incapable of solving internal problems and turned to metropolitan pundits for help (Nzongola 2002). Continued aid diplomacy and loans become the partnership model between Europeans and Africans. It demonstrates how Europeans could not understand that it would be a hurdle for Europe as long as African states could not resolve their problems. Leaders enjoyed tremendous support from European civil society and charity organizations without any tangible impact of long-term improvement of social conditions (Ndayweill 2009). The post-dictatorship era did not bring anything new regarding the model of cooperation. However, individual European states find themselves outdated by China's strategic move in Africa. The good news is China does not seriously threaten European core interests in Africa. Several European leaders welcomed China's presence in Africa because it served their immediate and long-term interests. Recently, agreements were in progress, U.S. alike, to strengthen European-China's partnership in Africa (Gisela 2021).

The European core interests in Africa focuses on limiting immigration and monitoring terrorist expansion in the Sahel. One may object to referring to the correlation between young African will-power to immigrate to Europe and the European interest. Nevertheless, it is a matter of interdependencies and spillover in strategic studies. When one analyses what pushes young Africans to immigrate or become terrorists, it is usually the adverse effects of climate change,

poverty, and despair. More importantly, in 1950, the combined European population (379 million) was nearly double that of Africa's (229 million). Today, Africa's population (1.5 billion in 2018) is double that of the European countries (513 million in 2018). Before the end of the 21st century, Africa's population is projected to be almost ten times larger (4.5 billion) compared to that of Europe (493 million) (Kishore, 2020). Another critical factor is climate change. For instance, the diminishing of Chad Lake has affected many who depend on it for livelihood. As long as Africa faces climate change problems, Europe will continually receive migrants, climate refugees or at least live with unsafe conscientiousness seeing dying people on the Mediterranean Sea. It also contradicts the European belief system and Christian values.

Therefore, European strategy in Africa should be welcoming economic and social change in Africa and work in partnership with the African Union to promote multilateralism to address the socio-political problems crippling African states. Since 21st-century challenges are non-traditional (Pandemics, climate change, terrorism, etc.), multi-lateral forums and consensus are required to address the issues. Africa must be enabled to take a leadership role in these areas for a common destiny for humankind.

Why Europe faces a choice dilemma?

The European Choice dilemma is related to the conflictual nature underlining the Post-cold war US-China competition for world primacy. In the International Relations realist school of thought perspective, great powers competition is a zero sum game. So, Europe or its states might face the choice dilemma of choosing the U.S. camp or the China one.

Historically and culturally, Europe belongs to the western side. International Relations is about interest rather than geography or culture; thus, Europe is puzzled by its limited options in Africa. China is doing remarkably good in improving African conditions through its overall

engagements. However, it is equally vital for Europe and America to cooperate with China in Africa. Since the American secretary of State warned Europe from aligning with the Chinese, European states, namely France and Germany, started prioritizing their national interests with China rather than on collective interest. This is a choice dilemma for Europe.

Future historians are waiting for a thoughtful European strategy to emerge to manage the Post-cold war US-China competition for world primacy, especially in Africa.

Conclusion

This paper briefly explained why Europe faces a choice dilemma in Africa under the Post-cold war US-China competition for world primacy. It further demonstrated that European peace in the 21st century depends mainly on African stability. For two decades, China has done much more than any other country on the African rise story. Today's overall US-China worldwide competition negatively affects this odyssey. However, cultural affinity cannot overcome geopolitical realities. How Europe will thoughtfully manage US-China dynamics is a century question and before Europe faces a choice dilemma.

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